

Highlights

Local-nonlocal stress-driven model for multi-cracked nanobeams

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- Nonlocal stress-driven model (SDM) for nanobeams with an arbitrary number of cracks
- Exact closed-form solutions
- Solution based on the integral definition of the SDM
- Solution based on a differential equation with constitutive boundary conditions
- Deflection line without slope discontinuity in contrast to local elasticity

Local-nonlocal stress-driven model for multi-cracked nanobeams

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Abstract

Exact closed-form solutions for multi-cracked Euler-Bernoulli nanobeams are provided by proposing two equivalent approaches. The considered multi-cracked nanobeams are modeled with a well-posed local-nonlocal stress-driven model and contain an arbitrary number n of isolated damaged cross sections. In order to simulate the damaged sections, it is assumed that the nanobeam bending flexibility contains n Dirac delta functions, with a Dirac delta located at each damaged section: this representation of cracked sections, already used in local problem, is adopted for the first time here in the local-nonlocal stress-driven model. The first approach providing closed-form solutions is based on the integral definition of the local-nonlocal stress-driven model, where the bending curvature is given by the superposition of the local and nonlocal phases, and the nonlocal phase is an integral convolution of the bending moment. This approach provides an integro-differential equation, which is solved by taking firstly the Laplace transform and then the anti-transform. In the second approach, it is shown that the integral definition of the stress-driven multi-cracked nanobeam model is equivalent to

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a differential equation together with suitable constitutive boundary conditions. This equation is solved by making use of Laplace transform again. The two approaches provide the same solution, with the second one resulting computationally faster. Interesting results show that a jump of rotation at the damaged cross sections occurs in local beam, but does not occur in pure nonlocal nanobeams (i.e. local phase is absent): contrary to the local elasticity theory, the bending curvature of pure nonlocal nanobeams has no singularity at damaged sections. The typical stiffness increase, due to the increase in nonlocal fraction of the mixture or to the increase in the length-scale parameter, also appears in multi-cracked nanobeams and this stiffening nonlocal effect is more pronounced in more constrained nanobeams.

Keywords: Nanobeam, Nonlocal theory, Crack, Dirac Delta

1. Introduction

Recent nanoscale technology has involved a great development of nanomechanics for investigating the mechanical behavior of different types of nanostructures and nanosystems, such as nanorods, nanowires, nanotubes, nanoribbons, nanoshells, etc. Typical applications of nanomechanics are nanoelectromechanical systems (NEMS) and microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) (Ekinici and Roukes, 2005; Li et al., 2007). Appropriate theoretical methods for the mechanics of nanostructures, such as molecular dynamics, result computationally expensive. Therefore, many authors have adopted methods based on generalized continuum mechanics (Maugin, 2017) oriented to small-scale effects in nanostructures, see e.g. nonlocal mechanics (Eringen, 1972, 1992; Peddieson et al., 2003; Wang and Liew, 2007; Nazmul and Devnath, 2021), strain gradient elasticity and couple stress models (Akgöz and Civalek, 2011). In nonlocal models, the response at a point depends on the value of a source not only at that point but also in a neighborhood of that point. Nonlocal models are largely used in nanomechanics, but they find application also in a different branch of mechanics, that is quasi-brittle materials, impact mechanics and high-energy absorbing materials (Qiao et al., 2008; Sun et al., 2009): as a matter of fact, nonlocal models offer the advantage of avoiding mesh sensitivity in numerical computations, regularizing strain softening and preventing nonphysical responses, such as premature crack initiation, instantaneous perfectly brittle crack growth and instantaneous failure in a vanishing volume. To this end, the improvement in nonlocal plasticity

24 and nonlocal damage performed by many authors (Eringen, 1981; Bažant
25 and Lin, 1988; Polizzotto et al., 1998; Peerlings et al., 2001, 2002; Desmorat
26 et al., 2007; Duddu and Waisman, 2013; Jirásek and Desmorat, 2019) are
27 noteworthy.

28 In both large- and small-scale applications, the beam elements are fre-
29 quently encountered. Defects, cracks and, more generally, damage in nanobeams
30 produce a reduction of stiffness, which have been studied in different situ-
31 ations. The effects of cracks have been investigated in: static bending of
32 a functionally graded Euler-Bernoulli cantilever nanobeam (Akbaş, 2018a);
33 buckling analysis of a cantilever nanobeam (Arif and Lellep, 2022); longitu-
34 dinal vibration (Hsu et al., 2011) and free transverse vibrations of Euler-
35 Bernoulli nanobeams (Loya et al., 2009; Roostai and Haghpanahi, 2014;
36 Loghmani and Hairi Yazdi, 2018), Timoshenko nanobeams (Torabi and Na-
37 far Dastgerdi, 2012; Hosseini-Hashemi et al., 2014), and functionally graded
38 nanobeam on elastic medium (Soltanpour et al., 2017); torsional vibration
39 (Rahmani et al., 2015); forced vibration responses of a cantilever Timoshenko
40 nanobeam (Akbaş, 2018b); thermal vibration analysis of nanobeams embed-
41 ded in an elastic matrix (Aria et al., 2019); vibration, wave power transmis-
42 sion and reflection in multi-cracked Euler-Bernoulli nanobeams (Bahrami,
43 2017); thermal and magnetic influence on vibration (Karličić et al., 2015)
44 and crack growth (Zhang et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2013).

45 Nonlocal models for cracked nanobeams have been used in Loya et al.
46 (2009), Hsu et al. (2011), Torabi and Nafar Dastgerdi (2012), Roostai and
47 Haghpanahi (2014), Soltanpour et al. (2017), Bahrami (2017), Loghmani
48 and Hairi Yazdi (2018) and Aria et al. (2019). Other Authors have adopted
49 the gradient elasticity theory (Zhang et al., 2013) or the couple stress theory
50 (Akbaş, 2018a,b). Many Authors have further expanded the application area
51 of the nonlocal theory by studying stress at crack tip of different solid types
52 (Zhou et al., 1999; Liu et al., 2015).

53 In order to overcome some inconsistencies emerged in nonlocal differen-
54 tial models, Romano et al. (2017) and Romano and Barretta (2017) have
55 introduced a stress-driven model where the input is the stress, in contrast
56 to strain-driven approaches, such as the Eringen differential nonlocal model,
57 where the input is the strain. The stress-driven model has been successfully
58 applied to solve many nonlocal problems (Luciano et al., 2020; Scorza et al.,
59 2021, 2022; Vantadori et al., 2022; Caporale et al., 2022; Darban et al., 2022b)
60 and, recently, has been used for cracked nanobeams modeled as segments
61 connected by rotational spring at the cracked section (Darban et al., 2022a;

62 Scorza et al., 2023). This spring approach is very common in nanomechanics, see e.g Loya et al. (2009), Hsu et al. (2011), Torabi and Nafar Dastgerdi
63 (2012), Roostai and Haghpanahi (2014), Hosseini-Hashemi et al. (2014), Rahmani et al. (2015), Karličić et al. (2015), Bahrami (2017), Soltanpour et al.
64 (2017), Loghmani and Hairi Yazdi (2018), Akbaş (2018a), Akbaş (2018b), Aria et al. (2019), where the cracked beam is modeled as separate segments
65 connected by axial, rotational or torsional springs located at the cracked
66 sections.
67

70 In this work, a local-nonlocal stress-driven model, consisting of the superposition of the local and pure nonlocal phases, is adopted for multi-cracked
71 nanobeams. In order to model the cracks, the nanobeam is not separated into segments connected by hinges with rotational springs at the cracked sections;
72 rather, the considered nanobeam is modeled as a continuous segment with variable bending flexibility, containing Dirac delta functions located at
73 cracked sections. The bending flexibility with Dirac delta functions has been used by Palmeri and Cicirello (2011) for treating cracks in local problems
74 (see also Cicirello and Palmeri, 2014; Cicirello, 2019) and it is here adopted for the first time in the stress-driven model. In local problems, the bending
75 flexibility with a Dirac delta produces a singularity of the bending curvature and a consequent slope discontinuity of the deflection line at the cracked
76 section. The same happens in a nanobeam modeled as separate segments connected by springs located at the cracked sections. On the other hand, in
77 this work it is shown that the bending flexibility with Dirac delta functions produces no singularity of the bending curvature in the pure nonlocal stress-driven
78 model, in accordance with nonlocal theory: see, e.g., the absence of stress singularity at crack tips of nonlocal structures (Zhou et al., 1999; Liu
79 et al., 2015), in contrast to the local elasticity theory.
80

81 The present paper is structured as follows. After defining the crack model in Section 2, two equivalent methods for obtaining closed-form solutions of
82 multi-cracked nanobeams are proposed, that is the integral method in Section 3.1 and the differential method in Section 3.2. Then, the obtained results are
83 presented for nanobeams with a single crack in Section 4.1, for moderately cracked nanobeams (i.e with few cracked cross sections) in Section 4.2.1 and
84 for extremely damaged nanobeams (i.e. with several dozens of cracked cross sections) in Section 4.2.2. The main conclusions are summarized in Section
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98 **2. Modeling of cracks in nanobeams**

99 The nanobeam under consideration is constituted of undamaged and dam-
 100 aged cross sections. By denoting with x the coordinate of the nanobeam
 101 axis, the generic damaged cross section is located at an abscissa $x = x_i$, with
 102 $i = 1, \dots, n$ and

$$0 = x_0 < x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_{i-1} < x_i < x_{i+1} < \dots < x_{n-1} < x_n < x_L, \quad (1)$$

103 where x_0 and x_L are the nanobeam left and right endpoints, respectively.
 104 The nanobeam is damaged at n isolated cross sections and both the ends
 105 of the nanobeam are assumed undamaged, for simplifying the formulation.
 106 The bending stiffness of the undamaged cross section is EI_0 , where E is the
 107 Young's modulus and I_0 is the second area moment of the undamaged cross
 108 section. Following Palmeri and Cicirello (2011), the bending flexibility is
 109 given by

$$\frac{1}{EI(x)} = \frac{1 + d_\delta(x)}{EI_0}. \quad (2)$$

110 being

$$d_\delta(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i \delta(x - x_i), \quad (3)$$

111 where $\delta(x)$ is the Dirac delta function and β_i is a constant accounting for
 112 severity/extent of damage in correspondence of the cross section at the ab-
 113 scissa x_i . In the framework of the local beam theory, Palmeri and Cicirello
 114 (2011) have shown that the damaged cross section modeled with a Dirac delta
 115 is equivalent to an internal hinge with a rotational spring, characterized by
 116 a stiffness depending on EI_0 and β_i . This equivalence between the internal
 117 spring and the damage cross section modeled with a Dirac delta is not true
 118 in some of the proposed nonlocal models, where the application of a Dirac
 119 delta at a given cross section not always produces a jump of rotation, as it
 120 would occur in presence of an internal hinge.

121 The bending flexibility given by Eq. (2) has been adopted for modeling
 122 cracks in both local (Cicirello and Palmeri, 2014; Cicirello, 2019) and nonlocal
 123 (Donà et al., 2014) beams. In the following, the above flexibility is used,
 124 for the first time, within a well-posed local-nonlocal stress-driven model,
 125 which solves some inconsistencies emerged in nonlocal differential models.
 126 Since the aim of this work is to evaluate the increase in deformability caused
 127 by a given configuration of cracked sections with a damage severity β_i (for

128 $i = 1, \dots, n$), as already performed by other Authors for local beams (Palmeri
 129 and Cicirello, 2011; Cicirello and Palmeri, 2014; Cicirello, 2019), it is assumed
 130 that all cracked sections have the same damage severity β_i . The definition of
 131 an evolution law for the damage parameter β_i and the correlation between β_i
 132 and the crack depth are out of the scope of this article and will be investigated
 133 in future works.

134 3. Local-nonlocal stress-driven model for multi-cracked nanobeams

135 Closed-form solutions for the bending problem of multi-cracked Euler-
 136 Bernoulli nanobeams are obtained through two different equivalent meth-
 137 ods, that is an integral method, proposed in Section 3.1, and a differential
 138 method, proposed in Section 3.2. The following Euler-Bernoulli relationship
 139 is assumed between the curvature χ and the transverse displacement v :

$$\chi(x) = D_x^2 v(x). \quad (4)$$

140 In this work, the k -th derivative of a generic function $f(x)$, with respect
 141 to the variable x , is denoted by $D_x^k f(x)$, with $D_x^1 f(x) = D_x f(x)$. Moreover,
 142 the k -th derivative of $f(x)$ evaluated at a given point \bar{x} is denoted by $D_x^k f(\bar{x})$.

143 3.1. The integral method

144 In the considered local-nonlocal stress-driven model, the kinematic effects
 145 are produced by the source

$$S(x) = M(x) \frac{1 + d_\delta(x)}{EI_0}, \quad (5)$$

146 where M is the bending moment, satisfying the equilibrium equations of the
 147 nanobeam, and d_δ is defined by Eq. (3). The bending curvature χ is given by
 148 the following convex combination (mixture) of the local and nonlocal parts:

$$\chi(x) = \alpha \chi_L(x) + (1 - \alpha) \chi_N(x), \quad (6)$$

where

$$\chi_L(x) = S(x), \quad (7)$$

$$\chi_N(x) = \int_{x_0}^{x_L} \psi(x - \xi, L_c) S(\xi) d\xi. \quad (8)$$

149 Being χ_L and χ_N the local and nonlocal phases of the mixture, respec-
 150 tively, the local-nonlocal mixture is governed by the parameter α varying
 151 between 0 and 1. The distance $x_L - x_0 > 0$ represents the length L of
 152 the nanobeam. The kernel function ψ depends on a length-scale paramete-
 153 ter $L_c \geq 0$. In Eq. (5), $(1 + d_\delta)/(EI_0)$ represents the bending flexibility
 154 $1/(EI(x))$, according to Eq. (2). Although $1/(EI(x))$ is usually assumed
 155 constant in stress-driven models available in existing literature, instead it is
 156 not constant in Eq. (6) since it contains Dirac delta functions. In order to
 157 facilitate the transition from integral to differential formulation of the prob-
 158 lem, a suitable choice of the kernel ψ in Eq. (8) is required (Romano and
 159 Barretta, 2017), and the kernel ψ is assumed equal to

$$\psi(x, L_c) = \frac{1}{2L_c} \exp\left(-\frac{|x|}{L_c}\right). \quad (9)$$

160 By taking into account Eqs. (2), (3) and (9), the nonlocal phase given by
 161 Eq. (8) becomes

$$\chi_N(x) = \chi_{N0}(x) + \chi_{Nd}(x), \quad (10)$$

where

$$\chi_{N0}(x) = \int_{x_0}^{x_L} \psi(x - \xi, L_c) \frac{M(\xi)}{EI_0} d\xi, \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_{Nd}(x) = & \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{M(x_i)}{EI_0} \beta_i \left[\exp\left(\frac{x_i - x}{L_c}\right) \frac{\mathcal{H}(x - x_i)}{2L_c} \right. \\ & \left. + \exp\left(\frac{x - x_i}{L_c}\right) \frac{\mathcal{H}(x_i - x)}{2L_c} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

162 being \mathcal{H} the Heaviside step function, defined as $\mathcal{H}(x) = 1$ for $x > 0$ and
 163 $\mathcal{H}(x) = 0$ for $x \leq 0$. χ_{N0} is the nonlocal contribution corresponding to
 164 the undamaged beam, so that the Euler-Bernoulli undamaged nanobeam is
 165 governed by the following equation:

$$\chi_0(x) = \alpha\chi_L(x) + (1 - \alpha)\chi_{N0}(x), \quad (13)$$

166 where $\chi_0 = D_x^2 v_0$ and v_0 are bending curvature and transverse displacement,
 167 respectively, of the undamaged nanobeam. By taking into account Eqs. (4)
 168 and (10), Eq. (6) becomes

$$D_x^2 v(x) = \alpha\chi_L(x) + (1 - \alpha) [\chi_{N0}(x) + \chi_{Nd}(x)], \quad (14)$$

169 which represents the equation governing the problem of a multi-cracked
 170 Euler-Bernoulli stress-driven nanobeam. The integro-differential equation
 171 (14) can be solved in a straightforward way by dividing the interval (x_0, x_L)
 172 of integration into two parts, so that the integrand is no longer discontinuous.

173 In order to obtain an exact solution of the problem, the Laplace transform
 174 of both sides of the integro-differential equation (14) is performed, providing:

$$s^2 \mathcal{L}\{v\}(s) + sc_3 + c_4 = \alpha \mathcal{L}\{\chi_L\}(s) + (1 - \alpha) [\mathcal{L}\{\chi_{N0}\}(s) + \mathcal{L}\{\chi_{Nd}\}(s)], \quad (15)$$

175 where $\mathcal{L}\{f\}(s)$ denotes the Laplace transform of function f and

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{L}\{\chi_L\}(s) = \frac{\mathcal{L}\{M\}(s)}{EI_0} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{M(x_i)}{EI_0} \beta_i \exp(-sx_i), \\ \mathcal{L}\{\chi_{N0}\}(s) = \frac{1}{2EI_0(sL_c - 1)} \left[\int_0^L M(\xi) \exp\left(-\frac{\xi}{L_c}\right) d\xi - \mathcal{L}\{M\}(s) \right] \\ \quad + \frac{\mathcal{L}\{M\}(s)}{2EI_0(sL_c + 1)}, \\ \mathcal{L}\{\chi_{Nd}\}(s) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n M(x_i) \beta_i \left[\frac{-2 \exp(-sx_i)}{sL_c + 1} + \exp\left(-\frac{x_i}{L_c}\right) \right]}{2EI_0(sL_c - 1)}. \end{array} \right. \quad (16)$$

In order to solve Eq. (15), the bending moment M is represented as a function of the distributed transverse load q , through the following relationships coming from equilibrium equations of the nanobeam:

$$V(x) = -D_x^{-1}q(x) + c_1, \quad (17)$$

$$M(x) = D_x^{-2}q(x) - c_1x + c_2, \quad (18)$$

176 where V is the shear force and $D_x^{-k}f$ is the k -th antiderivative of function f ,
 177 i.e. $D_x^k D_x^{-k}f = f$. By adopting the following polynomial expression for the
 178 distributed load q :

$$q(x) = \sum_{k=0}^m a_k x^k, \quad (19)$$

179 the bending moment M is given by

$$M(x) = \sum_{k=0}^m \frac{a_k x^{k+2}}{(k+2)(k+1)} - c_1x + c_2 \quad \text{for } x \in (x_0, x_L) \quad (20)$$

180 and its relevant Laplace transform is

$$\mathcal{L}\{M\}(s) = \sum_{k=0}^m \frac{a_k (k+2)!}{(k+2)(k+1)s^{k+3}} - \frac{c_1}{s^2} + \frac{c_2}{s}. \quad (21)$$

181 For any given value of the upper bound m of summation in Eq. (21),
 182 the inverse Laplace transform of Eq. (15) supplies a closed-form solution for
 183 the displacement v of multi-cracked nanobeams. In Section 4, suggestions
 184 on the fastest procedure for obtaining closed-form solutions for multi-cracked
 185 nanobeams are presented.

186 3.2. The differential method

187 The problem defined in Section 3.1 can be stated in an equivalent differ-
 188 ential form. It results as

$$\chi_N(x) = \chi_{N,Lt}(x) + \chi_{N,Rt}(x), \quad (22)$$

189 where

$$\begin{cases} \chi_{N,Lt}(x) = \int_{x_0}^x \psi(x-\xi, L_c) S(\xi) d\xi \\ \chi_{N,Rt}(x) = \int_x^{x_L} \psi(x-\xi, L_c) S(\xi) d\xi, \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

with the source S defined by Eq. (5). The first and second derivatives of $\chi_N(x)$ are given by:

$$D_x \chi_N(x) = \frac{1}{L_c} [-\chi_{N,Lt}(x) + \chi_{N,Rt}(x)], \quad (24)$$

$$D_x^2 \chi_N(x) = \frac{1}{L_c^2} [\chi_N(x) - S(x)], \quad (25)$$

190 respectively. By substituting Eq. (25) into the second derivative of Eq.
 191 (6) and by taking into account Eqs. (3) and (4), the following fourth-order
 192 differential equation governing the problem of multi-cracked Euler-Bernoulli
 193 nanobeams, modeled with the stress-driven model, is obtained:

$$D_x^4 v(x) - \frac{1}{L_c^2} D_x^2 v(x) = \alpha D_x^2 S(x) - \frac{1}{L_c^2} S(x). \quad (26)$$

194 The general solution of the ordinary differential equation (26) contains
 195 four constants of integration, which are determined by imposing the follow-
 196 ing four boundary conditions (BC) at endpoints of the interval (x_0, x_L) : two

197 standard BC, also prescribed in local problem, and two constitutive BC spe-
 198 cific for nonlocal problems. The constitutive BC are obtained by evaluating
 199 the first derivative of $\chi_N(x)$ at the endpoints x_0 and x_L , by using Eq. (24):

$$\begin{cases} D_x \chi_N(x_0) = \frac{1}{L_c} \chi_N(x_0), \\ D_x \chi_N(x_L) = -\frac{1}{L_c} \chi_N(x_L). \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

200 Observing that $\chi_N = (\chi - \alpha S)/(1 - \alpha)$, the following constitutive BC are
 201 obtained from Eq. (27)

$$\begin{cases} D_x^3 v(x_0) - \frac{1}{L_c} D_x^2 v(x_0) = \alpha D_x S(x_0) - \frac{\alpha}{L_c} S(x_0), \\ D_x^3 v(x_L) + \frac{1}{L_c} D_x^2 v(x_L) = \alpha D_x S(x_L) + \frac{\alpha}{L_c} S(x_L). \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

202 It is worth noting that BC given by Eq. (28) do not contain a Dirac delta,
 203 since both the ends of the nanobeam are assumed undamaged for simplifying
 204 the formulation.

205 An exact solution of the problem is obtained by performing the Laplace
 206 transform of both the sides of the differential equation (26), i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(s^4 - \frac{s^2}{L_c^2} \right) \mathcal{L}\{v\}(s) + \left(s^3 - \frac{s}{L_c^2} \right) c_6 + \left(s^2 - \frac{1}{L_c^2} \right) c_5 + s c_4 + c_3 = \\ & \frac{1}{EI_0} \left[-\frac{1}{L_c^2} + \alpha s^2 \right] \left[\mathcal{L}\{M\}(s) + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i M(x_i) \exp(-s x_i) \right] \\ & - \frac{\alpha}{EI_0} [sM(0) + D_x M(0)]. \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

207 In Eq. (29), it has been taken into account that the left end section of
 208 the nanobeam is undamaged (i.e. $x_i \neq x_0 = 0$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$), so that it
 209 follows

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[M(x) \left(1 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i \delta(x - x_i) \right) \right]_{x=0} = M(0), \\ & \left[D_x M(x) \left(1 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i \delta(x - x_i) \right) + M(x) \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i D_x \delta(x - x_i) \right) \right]_{x=0} = D_x M(0), \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

210 where $[f(x)]_{x=\bar{x}}$ denotes the value of $f(x)$ at point $x = \bar{x}$.

211 By replacing $\mathcal{L}\{M\}(s)$ in Eq. (29) with the right-hand side of Eq. (21),
 212 it provides

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}\{v\}(s) = & \left\{ \frac{1}{EI_0 L_c^2} \left(\frac{c_1}{s^2} - \frac{c_2}{s} \right) + \frac{1}{EI_0} \left[-\frac{1}{L_c^2} + \alpha s^2 \right] \left[\sum_{k=0}^m \frac{a_k k!}{s^{k+3}} \right. \right. \\ & + \left. \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i \exp(-s x_i) \left(\frac{a_k x_i^{k+2}}{(k+2)(k+1)} - c_1 x_i + c_2 \right) \right] \\ & \left. - \left(s^3 - \frac{s}{L_c^2} \right) c_6 - \left(s^2 - \frac{1}{L_c^2} \right) c_5 - s c_4 - c_3, \right\} \left(s^4 - \frac{s^2}{L_c^2} \right)^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

213 For any value of m , the inverse Laplace transform of Eq. (31) supplies a
 214 closed-form solution for the displacement v of multi-cracked nanobeams. A
 215 case of practical interest is $m = 0$ and $a_0 = q$, corresponding to a constant
 216 distributed load q . In this case, the inverse Laplace transform of Eq. (31)
 217 provides the following transverse displacement:

$$v(x) = v_0(x) + v_d(x), \quad (32)$$

218 where

$$\begin{cases} v_0(x) = v_I(x) + \alpha v_{II}(x), \\ v_d(x) = v_{Id}(x) + \alpha v_{IIId}(x), \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

219 and

$$\begin{cases} v_I(x) = \frac{L_c^2}{EI_0} \left\{ L_c [c_1 + EI_0 c_3] \sinh \left(\frac{x}{L_c} \right) + [-c_2 + EI_0 c_4 - L_c^2 q] \cosh \left(\frac{x}{L_c} \right) \right. \\ \quad \left. + \frac{q}{2} x^2 - c_1 x + c_2 + q L_c^2 \right\} - L_c^2 (c_3 x + c_4) \\ \quad + \frac{1}{EI_0} \left[\frac{q}{24} x^4 - \frac{1}{6} c_1 x^3 + c_2 \frac{x^2}{2} \right] + x c_5 + c_6, \\ v_{II}(x) = \frac{q L_c^2}{EI_0} \left[L_c^2 \cosh \left(\frac{x}{L_c} \right) - \frac{x^2}{2} - L_c^2 \right], \\ v_{Id}(x) = \frac{1}{EI_0} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathcal{H}(x - x_i) M(x_i) \beta_i \left[-L_c \sinh \left(\frac{x - x_i}{L_c} \right) + x - x_i \right], \\ v_{IIId}(x) = \frac{L_c}{EI_0} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathcal{H}(x - x_i) M(x_i) \beta_i \sinh \left(\frac{x - x_i}{L_c} \right). \end{cases} \quad (34)$$

220 In Eq. (32), v_0 and v_d are the contributions given by the undamaged and
 221 the damaged nanobeam, respectively.

222 4. Applications

223 The integral method proposed in Section 3.1 is equivalent to the differ-
 224 ential method derived in Section 3.2: the two methods involve two different
 225 procedures that provide the same exact solution. However, the differential
 226 procedure proposed in Section 3.2 is quite faster than the integral method and
 227 it is used in following applications providing closed-form solutions for sev-
 228 eral practical case-studies. More precisely, Section 4.1 deals with nanobeams
 229 damaged by a single crack located at an internal point of the nanobeam.
 230 Section 4.2 treats nanobeams with several cracks located at internal points
 231 of the nanobeam. Both local and nonlocal problems are significantly affected
 232 by standard boundary conditions. Thus, the proposed applications consider
 233 the following four different types of nanobeams:

- 234 • Simply supported nanobeam subject to a uniformly distributed trans-
 235 verse load q ; this type of nanobeam is denoted by acronym SSq and it
 236 is characterized by the standard boundary conditions (SBC):

$$\begin{cases} v(x_0) = 0, & M(x_0) = 0, \\ v(x_L) = 0, & M(x_L) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

- 237 • Fixed nanobeam subject to a uniformly distributed transverse load q ;
 238 this type is denoted by CCq and it is characterized by the SBC:

$$\begin{cases} v(x_0) = 0, & \varphi(x_0) = 0, \\ v(x_L) = 0, & \varphi(x_L) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (36)$$

- 239 • Cantilever nanobeam subject to a transverse force F concentrated at
 240 the right endpoint; this type is denoted by CF and has the SBC:

$$\begin{cases} v(x_0) = 0, & \varphi(x_0) = 0, \\ M(x_L) = 0, & V(x_L) = F. \end{cases} \quad (37)$$

- 241 • Cantilever nanobeam subject to a couple m concentrated at the right
 242 endpoint; this type is denoted by Cm and has the SBC:

$$\begin{cases} v(x_0) = 0, \varphi(x_0) = 0, \\ M(x_L) = m, V(x_L) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (38)$$

243 where $\varphi(x) = D_x v(x)$ is the rotation of cross section at the abscissa x of the
 244 nanobeam.

245 *4.1. Nanobeams with a single crack*

246 This section considers several types of straight nanobeam containing a
 247 single crack at the middle point. By assuming that the nanobeam left and
 248 right endpoints have abscissas $x_0 = 0$ and $x_L = L$, respectively, the single
 249 crack is located at the dimensionless abscissa $x/L = 0.5$ and is characterized
 250 by $\beta_1 = 1$. The results in Sections 4.1 and 4.2 are presented in a dimension-
 251 less form, by defining the following dimensionless loads: $\bar{q} = qL^3/(EI_0) = 1$,
 252 $\bar{F} = FL^2/(EI_0) = 1$ and $\bar{m} = mL/(EI_0) = 1$. In order to have an idea of
 253 the damage severity induced by $\beta = 1$, the dimensionless deflection line v/L
 254 is plotted against x/L in Figure 1 for local beams and nonlocal nanobeams,
 255 without and with a central crack. Local beams are obtained by setting $\alpha = 1$;
 256 for nonlocal nanobeams, a mixture with $\alpha = 0.5$ and $\lambda_c = 0.4$ is assumed.
 257 The absence of crack is obtained by setting $\beta = 0$ and its presence is given
 258 by $\beta = 1$. Figures 1a, 1b, 1c and 1d refer, respectively, to simply supported
 259 nanobeams with $\bar{q} = 1$ (SSq), fixed nanobeams with $\bar{q} = 1$ (CCq), cantilever
 260 nanobeams with a transverse force concentrated at $x/L = 1$ and character-
 261 ized by $\bar{F} = 1$ (CF), and cantilever nanobeams with a couple concentrated
 262 at $x/L = 1$ and characterized by $\bar{m} = 1$ (Cm).

263 In Figure 2, the dimensionless transverse displacement v/L is plotted
 264 against x/L for different values of the parameter α and for $\lambda_c = L_c/L = 0.2$.
 265 Each curve represents the dimensionless deflection line, that is the graph of
 266 the function

$$\bar{v}(\bar{x}) = v(\bar{x}L)/L \quad \text{with} \quad \bar{x} = x/L \quad (39)$$

267 corresponding each curve to a given value of α . The geometry, standard
 268 boundary conditions and external loads for Figures 2a, 2b, 2c and 2d are
 269 the same of those of Figures 1a, 1b, 1c and 1d, respectively. In Figure 2,
 270 the parameter α varies between 0 and 1, with an increment equal to 0.1.
 271 According to the integral model given by Eq. (6), the value $\alpha = 0$ represents

272 the pure nonlocal model (absence of the local fraction of the mixture) and
 273 the value $\alpha = 1$ represents the local beam (absence of the nonlocal fraction
 274 of the mixture). The intermediate values of α represents a mixture. Figure
 275 2 shows the well-known stiffening behavior of the stress-driven model: by
 276 increasing the nonlocal fraction of the mixture (i.e. by decreasing α), the
 277 nanobeam deformability (represented by the transverse displacement) de-
 278 creases, especially in simply supported (SSq) and fixed (CCq) schemes. This
 279 is due to the stiffness increase induced by the increase in the nonlocal frac-
 280 tion of the mixture. In the cantilever nanobeams (CF and Cm), on the other
 281 hand, the dimensionless deflection line is almost the same between the fixed
 282 left endpoint and the crack position (i.e. for x/L in the interval $(0, 0.5)$),
 283 showing that nanobeams are weakly affected by α in this portion of beam:
 284 such a behavior does not depend on the type of loads, as it also appears in
 285 cantilever nanobeams without concentrated forces or couples and subject to
 286 distributed load (not shown in the figure for brevity). In the remaining por-
 287 tion of nanocantilevers, from the cracked cross section to the right endpoint of
 288 the nanobeam, the stiffness increase induced by the nonlocal fraction is more
 289 evident and dimensionless deflection is noticeably affected by the parameter
 290 α . In the cantilever nanobeams with a couple applied at one endpoint (Cm),
 291 an unusual stiffness decrease, induced by nonlocal fraction, is also observed
 292 near the crack position.

293 By denoting with $\bar{v}_{upper}(\bar{x})$ and $\bar{v}_{lower}(\bar{x})$ the black and red curves of Figure
 294 2b, respectively, the relative distance of the two curves is given by:

$$\max_{\bar{x} \in [0,1]} \frac{\bar{v}_{upper}(\bar{x}) - \bar{v}_{lower}(\bar{x})}{\bar{v}_{upper}(\bar{x})}. \quad (40)$$

295 The relative distance between black ($\alpha = 1$) and red ($\alpha = 0$) dimen-
 296 sionless deflection lines in Figure 2b (CCq) is greater than the same rela-
 297 tive distance observed in Figure 2a (SSq). Moreover, the relative distance
 298 between black and red dimensionless deflection lines in Figure 2a (SSq) is
 299 greater than the same relative distance observed in Figures 2c (CF) and
 300 2d (Cm). In summary, the stiffness increase, induced by the increase in
 301 nonlocal fraction, is more pronounced in more constrained nanostructures,
 302 where fixed nanobeams are considered more constrained than simply sup-
 303 ported nanobeams, which in turn are more constrained than nano-cantilevers.
 304 Nonlocal effects in the stress-driven model are responsible for the stiffening
 305 behavior and are greater in more constrained nanostructures.

306 Figure 2 also shows the following important result specific for nanostruc-
 307 tures. In local problems (Palmeri and Cicirello, 2011), a crack modeled with
 308 a Dirac delta in the bending flexibility is equivalent to a rotational spring
 309 that breaks the original integrity of the undamaged beam and creates a dis-
 310 continuity of rotation at the cracked section. This is evident in Figure 2,
 311 where the black dimensionless deflection lines corresponding to local beams
 312 ($\alpha = 1$) exhibit a slope discontinuity at the abscissa $x/L = 0.5$, where a
 313 crack is present. The jump of rotation occurring in the cracked section of
 314 local beams (black lines with $\alpha = 1$) vanishes in pure nonlocal nanobeams
 315 represented by the red lines ($\alpha = 0$). The local-nonlocal mixture ensures the
 316 presence of a local fraction together with a nonlocal fraction when $\alpha \in]0, 1[$
 317 and the local fraction of the mixture causes a jump of rotation in the cracked
 318 section. For this reason, the dimensionless deflection lines corresponding to
 319 $\alpha \neq 1$ also exhibit a slope discontinuity in correspondence of the cracked
 320 section at $x/L = 0.5$. On the other hand, the absence of slope discontinuity
 321 in pure nonlocal nanobeams ($\alpha = 0$) appears coherent with nonlocal theory,
 322 where an entity (such as the bending curvature) at a given point depends not
 323 only on the source in that point but also on the source in a neighborhood
 324 of the point. Contrary to local beams, the bending curvature of pure non-
 325 local nanobeams have no singularity at the damaged section. Similar effects
 326 have been observed in different applications of nonlocal models: for example,
 327 a stress singularity is absent at crack tip of nonlocal plate and 3D medium
 328 (Zhou et al., 1999; Liu et al., 2015), in contrast to the classical local elasticity
 329 solution.

330 Figure 3 shows the same above concepts under a different point of view:
 331 here, dimensionless transverse displacement v/L of nanobeams is plotted
 332 against x/L for different values of $\lambda_c = L_c/L$ and $\alpha = 0$ (pure nonlocal
 333 model). The dimensionless deflection lines of Figure 3 have no slope dis-
 334 continuity in correspondence of the cracked section at $x/L = 0.5$ since the
 335 local fraction of the mixture is absent ($\alpha = 0$). The pure nonlocal model
 336 tends to the local model when λ_c tends to zero: consequently, dimension-
 337 less deflection lines of Figure 3 corresponding to small values of λ_c have a
 338 high rate of change of the slope (similar to a slope discontinuity) near the
 339 cracked section at $x/L = 0.5$. Concisely, the deflection line of pure nonlocal
 340 nanobeams is very near to the deflection line of local beams when the length-
 341 scale dimensionless parameter λ_c is very small. By denoting with $\bar{v}_{upper}(\bar{x})$
 342 and $\bar{v}_{lower}(\bar{x})$ the red and black curves of Figure 3b, respectively, the relative
 343 distance of the two curves is given by Eq. (40). The relative distance between

344 red ($\lambda_c = 0.005$) and black ($\lambda_c = 0.5$) dimensionless deflection lines in Figure
 345 3b (CCq) is greater than the relevant relative distance observed in Figure 3a
 346 (SSq). The relative distance between red and black curves in Figure 3a (SSq)
 347 is greater than the relevant relative distance observed in Figures 3c (CF) and
 348 3d (Cm). Nonlocal effects in the stress-driven model are responsible for the
 349 stiffening behavior and are greater in more constrained nanostructures. Fig-
 350 ure 3 shows that the stiffening effect due to the increase in the parameter
 351 λ_c is more pronounced in more constrained nanostructures. The stiffening
 352 effect of λ_c , shown in Figure 3, is similar to the stiffening effect obtained by
 353 decreasing α (i.e. by increasing nonlocal fraction), as reported in Figure 2,
 354 since the two effects have the same nonlocal nature.

355 In Figure 4, the dimensionless displacement at the middle point ($x/L =$
 356 0.5) of simply supported and fixed nanobeams or at right endpoint ($x/L = 1$)
 357 of cantilever nanobeams is plotted against $\lambda_c = L_c/L$ for different values of
 358 α . Figure 4 confirms the stiffness increase induced by the decrease in α value
 359 and the increase in λ_c : the dimensionless displacement for a given value of α
 360 decreases when λ_c increases and the dimensionless displacement for a given
 361 value of λ_c decreases when α decreases. Figure 4 also shows the interaction
 362 between the two nonlocal parameters λ_c and α . In Figure 4a, the absolute
 363 value of the slope of a generic curve at a given value of λ_c increases with de-
 364 creasing α : in other words, the sensitivity of the dimensionless displacement
 365 to λ_c increases with increasing the nonlocal fraction of the mixture. The
 366 same happens in Figures 4b-4d. It is worth noting that each curve of Figure
 367 4 is plotted for $\lambda_c \in [0.001, 1]$, since the resolution of the differential equation
 368 governing the nonlocal problem becomes difficult for very small values of λ_c ;
 369 for this reason, the curves of Figure 4 do not appear to tend to the same
 370 local dimensionless displacement as λ_c tends to zero. The slope of the curves
 371 of Figure 4b (CCq) is almost zero for sufficiently large values of α . This does
 372 not happen in Figures 4a, 4c, 4d, where the slope of curves is always different
 373 from zero. This means that the nonlocal effect of stiffening increases with
 374 increasing the length-scale parameter λ_c , but in more constrained nanostruc-
 375 tures (such as fixed nanobeams) this nonlocal effect diminishes quickly with
 376 α and no further decrease in stiffness occurs for sufficiently large values of α .

377 In Figure 5, the rotation φ of nanobeam cross sections is plotted against
 378 x/L for different values of λ_c and $\alpha = 0$. The local fraction of the mixture
 379 is responsible for the jump of the rotation at the cracked section at the
 380 abscissa $x = 0.5L$. In the nanobeams considered in Figure 5, the local
 381 fraction is absent and, therefore, the rotation do not have a jump at the

382 cracked section. Consequently, the curves of Figure 5 are smooth function of
383 the dimensionless abscissa x/L , whereas the curves corresponding to small
384 values of λ_c exhibit a large rate of change at the cracked section, approaching
385 a jump for $\lambda_c = 0$ (local beam). Previously, it has been observed that the
386 stiffening effect due to the increase in the parameter λ_c is more pronounced
387 in more constrained nanostructures. This phenomenon is also present in the
388 graph of the rotation function φ . The maximum positive value of the black
389 curve ($\lambda_c = 0.5$) is much smaller than the maximum positive value of the
390 red curve ($\lambda_c = 0.005$) in Figure 5b, referring to the more constrained fixed
391 nanobeam (CCq). This is less pronounced in Figures 5a, 5c and 5d, referring
392 to less constrained nanobeams SSq, CF and Cm.

393 In Figure 6, the rotation φ of nanobeam cross sections is plotted against
394 x/L for different values of λ_c and $\alpha = 0.5$. In this case, the local fraction of
395 the mixture is present and, therefore, each curve of Figure 6 has a jump of
396 rotation at the cracked section at the abscissa $x = 0.5L$. The integral def-
397 inition given by Eq. (6) of the stress-driven model indicates that statically
398 determinate nanobeams with the same value of α (and, therefore, the same
399 amount of local fraction) also have the same value of rotation jump at the
400 cracked section. This clearly happens not only in Figure 6a, referring to stat-
401 ically determinate simply supported nanobeams SSq, but also in Figure 6b,
402 referring to statically indeterminate fixed nanobeams CCq. By denoting with
403 $\bar{v}_{upper}(\bar{x})$ and $\bar{v}_{lower}(\bar{x})$ the red and black curves of Figure 6a, respectively,
404 the relative distance of the two curves is given by Eq. (40). The presence
405 of local fraction reduces the amount of nonlocal effect and the consequent
406 stiffness increase with λ_c : as a matter of fact, the relative distance between
407 red and black curves in Figures 6a-6d is not as large as the same distance in
408 Figures 5a-5d referring to the case $\alpha = 0$ (absence of local fraction).

409 In Figure 7, the dimensionless bending curvature χL is plotted against
410 x/L for different values of $\lambda_c = L_c/L$ and $\alpha = 0$. The figure can be inter-
411 preted as follows: from the integral definition given by Eq. (6), the pure
412 nonlocal nanobeams considered in Figure 7 tend to local beams as λ_c tends
413 to zero and the curvature of local beams has a Dirac delta at the cracked
414 section. Therefore, the curvatures of Figure 7 tends to a Dirac Delta at the
415 cracked section as λ_c tends to zero. On the other hand, the curvature is finite
416 for $\lambda_c > 0$ implying that no jump of rotation occurs at the cracked section
417 of pure nonlocal nanobeams, as presented in previous figures.

418 *4.2. Multi-cracked nanobeams*

419 *4.2.1. Moderately damaged nanobeams*

420 This section considers straight nanobeams containing three isolated cracks.
421 The nanobeam left and right endpoints have abscissas $x_0 = 0$ and $x_L = L$,
422 respectively; the three isolated cracked sections are located at the dimension-
423 less abscissas $x/L = 0.4, 0.5, 0.6$ and are characterized by $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = 1$.
424 The results refer to the following dimensionless loads: $\bar{q} = qL^3/(EI_0) = 1$,
425 $\bar{F} = FL^2/(EI_0) = 1$ and $\bar{m} = mL/(EI_0) = 1$. In Figure 8, the dimension-
426 less transverse displacement v/L is plotted against x/L for different values
427 of the parameter α and for $\lambda_c = L_c/L = 0.2$. The same observations done
428 for Figure 2 are also valid for Figure 8. More precisely, the nanobeam de-
429 formability decreases with increasing the nonlocal fraction of the mixture
430 (i.e. by decreasing α). A slope discontinuity of the dimensionless deflec-
431 tion lines (i.e. a jump of rotation) at the three cracked sections is visible
432 in almost all the curves of Figure 8, except for the red curves, which repre-
433 sent the pure nonlocal nanobeams ($\alpha = 0$). As a matter of fact, the curves
434 different from the red one refer to nanobeams containing a local fraction,
435 which is responsible of the jump of rotation at the three cracked sections.
436 The stiffness increase, induced by the increase in nonlocal fraction (i.e. by
437 the decrease in α), is more pronounced in more constrained nanostructures,
438 such as fixed nanobeams (CCq). By denoting with $\bar{v}_{upper}(\bar{x})$ and $\bar{v}_{lower}(\bar{x})$ the
439 black and red curves of Figure 8b, respectively, the relative distance between
440 these two curves has been defined by Eq. (40) and it is greater than the
441 relevant relative distance observed in Figure 8a (SSq); the relative distance
442 between red and black curves in Figure 8a (SSq) is greater than the relevant
443 relative distance observed in Figures 8c (CF) and 8d (Cm).

444 In Figure 9, the rotation φ of nanobeam cross sections is plotted against
445 x/L for different values of λ_c and $\alpha = 0$. The considerations done for Figure
446 5 are also valid for Figure 9. In stress-driven local-nonlocal mixture, a jump
447 of rotation is caused by the local fraction of the mixture. Therefore, the
448 curves of Figure 9 are smooth without slope discontinuity (i.e. without jump
449 of rotation), as the local fraction is absent ($\alpha = 0$). The nanobeam behavior
450 tends to local beam as λ_c tends to zero: for very small values of λ_c , high
451 rate of change of the rotation φ occurs in Figure 9, approaching the typical
452 rotation jump of a local beam.

453 *4.2.2. Extremely damaged nanobeams*

454 In order to investigate the nonlocal behavior of extremely damaged nanos-
455 tructures, this section considers different types of nanobeams subjected to an
456 increasing number of equidistant isolated cracks. Specifically, each nanobeam
457 has n equidistant cracked sections and the dimensionless abscissa of the
458 generic i -th crack is $x_i/L = i/(n + 1)$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$. The behavior of
459 extremely damaged nanobeams is investigated by increasing the number of
460 cracks n up to very high values and by assuming that all cracks have the
461 same severity, i.e. $\beta_i = 1$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$. The results refer to the follow-
462 ing dimensionless loads: $\bar{q} = qL^3/(EI_0) = 1$, $\bar{F} = FL^2/(EI_0) = 1$ and
463 $\bar{m} = mL/(EI_0) = 1$. In Figure 10, the dimensionless displacement at middle
464 point ($x/L = 0.5$) of simply supported and fixed nanobeams and at right
465 endpoint ($x/L = 1$) of cantilever nanobeams is plotted against n for different
466 values of λ_c and $\alpha = 0$. For each curve, the colored circles (representing the
467 values calculated with the procedure presented in Section 3.2) are connected
468 by straight line segments. The figure shows a linear relationship between the
469 dimensionless displacement and the number n of cracked sections, for suffi-
470 ciently large values of n : as a matter of fact, the relationship is not linear
471 for small values of n , as it can be observed for the red curves in Figures 10a
472 and 10b. As expected, the relationship between dimensionless displacement
473 and n is strictly increasing, that is the displacement increases with increase
474 in the number of cracked sections, except in fixed nanobeams (Figure 10b)
475 for small values of n . In Figures 10a-10d, the slope of the curves at a given
476 value of n decreases with λ_c , showing a stiffness increase due to the nonlocal
477 part of the mixture: in other words, the larger the parameter λ_c , the smaller
478 the deformation increase caused by the increase in the number n of cracks.
479 This effect is particularly dramatic in Figure 10b (CCq), where the slope of
480 the green and yellow curves, corresponding to $\lambda_c = 0.4, 0.6$, respectively, are
481 quite smaller than the slope of the red curve corresponding to $\lambda_c = 1/100$
482 (i.e. a nearly local beam): this example shows that, in statically indetermi-
483 nate nanostructures such as fixed nanobeams (CCq), the stiffness increase,
484 due to the nonlocal behavior, is particularly strong in extremely damaged
485 nanobeams (i.e. containing several dozens of cracked sections). In Figures
486 10a (SSq), 10c (CF) and 10d (Cm) representing the behavior of statically
487 determinate nanostructures, the slope of the curves gradually decreases by
488 passing from $\lambda_c = 1/1000$ to $\lambda_c = 0.6$, in contrast with the behavior shown
489 in Figure 10b (CCq), where the slope abruptly diminishes by passing from

490 $\lambda_c = 1/100$ to $\lambda_c = 0.2$ and, consequently, the displacements also diminish a
491 lot.

492 5. Conclusions

493 The multi-cracked nanobeams under consideration contain an arbitrary
494 number n of isolated damaged sections located at internal points of the
495 nanobeams. The bending flexibility contain n Dirac delta functions, with
496 each Dirac delta located at a damaged section. Some authors (Palmeri and
497 Cicirello, 2011; Cicirello and Palmeri, 2014; Cicirello, 2019) have used this
498 technique for representing damaged internal sections in local problems, ob-
499 serving that the Dirac delta in bending flexibility of local beams is equivalent
500 to an internal hinge equipped with a rotational spring and it produces a jump
501 of rotation in damaged sections. In this work, the bending flexibility con-
502 taining Dirac delta functions is used for the first time in the local-nonlocal
503 stress-driven model, i.e. a convex combination (mixture) of the local and
504 nonlocal phases, with nonlocal phase given by the integral convolution of
505 bending moment over the nanobeam length. The amount of the local and
506 nonlocal phases in the mixture is governed by the parameter α : the mixture
507 containing both the local and nonlocal phases is given by $0 < \alpha < 1$, whereas
508 $\alpha = 0$ provides the pure nonlocal model (without local phase) and $\alpha = 1$
509 gives a local beam.

510 Two equivalent approaches are proposed for finding exact closed-form
511 solutions of multi-cracked nanobeams. The first approach is based on the
512 integral definition of the local-nonlocal stress-driven model, which provides
513 an integro-differential equation solved by using the Laplace transform and
514 anti-transform. In the second approach, it is shown that the integral formu-
515 lation of stress-driven multi-cracked nanobeams is equivalent to a differential
516 equation together with suitable constitutive boundary conditions; by tak-
517 ing firstly the Laplace transform and then anti-transform of the differential
518 equation, the solution of the problem is obtained.

519 The results are strongly affected by standard boundary conditions. There-
520 fore, different types of boundary constraints and loads are considered in
521 the computations: namely, simply supported nanobeams with a uniformly
522 distributed load (SSq), fixed nanobeams with a uniformly distributed load
523 (CCq), nanocantilevers with a transverse point load (CF) or a couple (Cm)
524 concentrated at one end-point of the nanobeam.

525 As expected, local beams obtained by setting $\alpha = 1$ in the local-nonlocal
526 mixture have a jump of rotation at damaged sections. On the other hand,
527 pure nonlocal nanobeams obtained by setting $\alpha = 0$ have no jumps of rotation
528 at damaged sections, showing a clear difference between local and nonlocal
529 behavior. Contrary to local beams, the bending curvature of pure nonlocal
530 nanobeams have no singularity at damaged section. This kind of regulariza-
531 tion produced by nonlocal models can be found in other works available in
532 literature: see, e.g., the absence of stress singularity at crack tips of nonlocal
533 plate and 3D medium (Zhou et al., 1999; Liu et al., 2015), in contrast to the
534 local elasticity theory. In the stress-driven mixture containing both the local
535 and nonlocal phases ($0 < \alpha < 1$), jumps of rotation (caused by local phase
536 of the mixture) occur at damaged sections.

537 A typical behavior of the stress-driven model is the stiffness increase
538 due to the increase in the nonlocal fraction of the mixture (by decreas-
539 ing α) or to the increase in the length-scale parameter λ_c . This effect is
540 also confirmed in multi-cracked nanobeams and it is more pronounced in
541 more constrained nanostructures, with the assumption that fixed nanobeams
542 are more constrained than simply supported nanobeams, which in turn are
543 more constrained than nanocantilevers. The augmentation of this stiffening
544 effect in more constrained structures appears in both moderately cracked
545 nanobeams (i.e. containing few cracked cross sections) and extremely dam-
546 aged nanobeams (i.e. containing several dozens of cracked cross sections),
547 resulting particularly dramatic in the latter, where the displacement greatly
548 decreases with slowly increasing λ_c .

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Figure 1: Dimensionless transverse displacement v/L plotted against x/L for local beams and nonlocal nanobeams, without and with a central crack ($\alpha = 0.5$ and $\lambda_c = 0.4$ for nonlocal nanobeams): (a) simply supported beams/nanobeams with a uniformly distributed load; (b) fixed beams/nanobeams with a uniformly distributed load; (c) cantilever beams/nanobeams with a force concentrated at the right endpoint; and (d) cantilever beams/nanobeams with a couple concentrated at the right endpoint.

Figure 2: Dimensionless transverse displacement v/L of beams/nanobeams plotted against x/L for different values of α and $\lambda_c = L_c/L = 0.2$: (a) simply supported beams/nanobeams with a uniformly distributed load; (b) fixed beams/nanobeams with a uniformly distributed load; (c) cantilever beams/nanobeams with a force concentrated at the right endpoint; and (d) cantilever beams/nanobeams with a couple concentrated at the right endpoint.

Figure 3: Dimensionless transverse displacement v/L of nanobeams plotted against x/L for different values of $\lambda_c = L_c/L$ and $\alpha = 0$: (a) simply supported nanobeams with a uniformly distributed load; (b) fixed nanobeams with a uniformly distributed load; (c) cantilever nanobeams with a force concentrated at the right endpoint; and (d) cantilever nanobeams with a couple concentrated at the right endpoint.

Figure 4: Dimensionless displacement at the middle point (for simply supported and fixed beams/nanobeams) or at the right end (for cantilever beams/nanobeams) plotted against $\lambda_c = L_c/L$ for different values of α .

Figure 5: Cross sectional rotation plotted against x/L for different values of $\lambda_c = L_c/L$ and $\alpha = 0$: (a) simply supported nanobeams with a uniformly distributed load; (b) fixed nanobeams with a uniformly distributed load; (c) cantilever nanobeams with a force concentrated at the right endpoint; and (d) cantilever nanobeams with a couple concentrated at the right endpoint.

Figure 6: Cross sectional rotation plotted against x/L for different values of $\lambda_c = L_c/L$ and $\alpha = 0.5$: (a) simply supported nanobeams with a uniformly distributed load; (b) fixed nanobeams with a uniformly distributed load; (c) cantilever nanobeams with a force concentrated at the right endpoint; and (d) cantilever nanobeams with a couple concentrated at the right endpoint.

Figure 7: Dimensionless bending curvature plotted against x/L for different values of $\lambda_c = L_c/L$ and $\alpha = 0$: (a) simply supported nanobeams with a uniformly distributed load; (b) fixed nanobeams with a uniformly distributed load; (c) cantilever nanobeams with a force concentrated at the right endpoint; and (d) cantilever nanobeams with a couple concentrated at the right endpoint.

Figure 8: Dimensionless transverse displacement v/L of beams/nanobeams with three cracks plotted against x/L for different values of α and for $\lambda_c = L_c/L = 0.2$: (a) simply supported beams/nanobeams with a uniformly distributed load; (b) fixed beams/nanobeams with a uniformly distributed load; (c) cantilever beams/nanobeams with a force concentrated at the right endpoint; and (d) cantilever beams/nanobeams with a couple concentrated at the right endpoint.

Figure 9: Cross sectional rotation of nanobeams with three cracks for different values of $\lambda_c = L_c/L$ and $\alpha = 0$: (a) simply supported nanobeams with a uniformly distributed load; (b) fixed nanobeams with a uniformly distributed load; (c) cantilever nanobeams with a force concentrated at the right endpoint; and (d) cantilever nanobeams with a couple concentrated at the right endpoint.

Figure 10: Dimensionless displacement at the middle point (for simply supported and fixed nanobeams) and at the right end (for cantilever nanobeams) plotted against the number n of cracked cross sections, for different values of $\lambda_c = L_c/L$.